

BETWEEN EARTH AND HEAVEN: THE RELIGIOUS PRESENCE IN BRAZIL'S CULTURAL AND LEGAL CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract: The purpose of this paper is to analyze the complex relationship between religion and politics in Brazil, under a historical and cultural perspective grounded on a political reality. It investigates religious impartiality on issues of political interest and religious presence in political debates. It observes the great religious influence in the elections and the use of Christian values in Brazilian society as a basis for defending conservative agendas opposed to the rights of minorities. It examines the need for a legal and philosophical reflection on the relationship between religion and politics concerning State Secularism, encouraging the academic discussion related to the historical, political and cultural aspects of Law. It reflects the coexistence between political and religious spheres, as well as their contribution in the legal and cultural construction of Brazilian Identity.

Keywords: Politics, Religion; Secular State; Philosophy of Law; Political Philosophy;

1 BETWEEN LAITY AND CHRISTIAN CULTURE: CURRENT CHALLENGES

The heated discussions regarding the secularity of the State have been very common, and the principle of secularism is frequently used in the public space by politicians, social movements and representatives of the most different religious denominations. However, the troubled current scenario is permeated by questioning and criticism of the expression of the population's religious feeling, often associated with criticism and denial of scientific theories as well as the delay in cultural and economic development. Most of the time such discourses link religion as a legacy of obscurantism.

It is observed that religions often end up interfering in specific matters of public authorities, seeking to prevail in their way of understanding the world. It seems that they intend to impose their doctrine and that their dogmas prevail over democratic principles. This becomes a reason for conflicts between political and religious powers, as the public space is conceived

as *impervious* to the collaboration of traditional values, as it has been freed from *religious pressure* (ALMEIDA, 2013) .

However, the principle of the secularity of the State does not prevent religion from discussing concepts related to life in the public space in the face of the challenges of science and new technologies. Nor does it prevent analyzing such issues from the point of view of moral and religious values, since the Christian tradition is rooted in Western culture (VAZ, 2002) . One cannot forget that religion is power, and must be understood as something much more important than a mere matter of belief. Therefore, a reflection on this theme is opportune, analyzing the connection of religious power as a determining element in the structuring of western culture and, in a very particular way, in relation to Brazil, as a constitutive element in national formation.

2 THE RELIGIOUS PHENOMENON

The religious phenomenon presents itself as a symbolically plural fact, founding the relationships of life and establishing itself as an essential part of culture. In this sense, religion is not limited to a spiritual or transcendental dimension. More than that, it allows various forms of reading or interpretation, supported by the culture to convey its conception of divinity, its doctrinal body, its norms as the foundation of religious and political power (VAZ, 2002). Religion is established as doubly cultural, since it shows itself dialectically, as it influences cultures and societies and at the same time is influenced by cultural elements from which it develops.

Throughout history, we have witnessed the fruitful creative process that is always organizing the raw material of life and human experience, so that it is possible to transmit these existential values that constitute our rich cultural treasure (TAYLOR, 2010). The contribution of countless elements from the customs of different peoples, patiently absorbed and merged, balancing and stabilizing these cultural variations in a silent growth, provides the flowering and maturity of a culture (DAWSON, 2010).

The movement of intertwining concepts and values produced in other times can be found today, which makes evident the unity in the historical future and, therefore, reveals that, without the past, we would not be able to know the present (HORTA, 2013). In this perspective, we understand that it is necessary to emphasize that the religious dimension is expressed at the deep level of culture, a proper scope of existential questioning, of the formulation of meaning and of openness to the transcendent (TILLICH, 1999) . Religious experience manifests itself

as a way of understanding reality. Habits and customs that motivate actions are permeated by the understanding of reality, which uses religious interpretation and becomes the dimension that distinguishes human activities, such as ethics (VAZ, 2002).

When reflecting on the meaning and value of things, the opening to a non-immediatist perspective begins, but one that glimpses an existential reality. Religious consciousness is the experience of an ultimate, unconditional meaning that takes place within everyday reality. Religion is expressed in culture, just as the substance of culture is expressed in religion, as a mark that intertwines with the way of understanding reality, as a source of meaning. This is evident in the religious experience, constituting one of the richest heuristic matrices that allow us to interpret the symbolic universes that guided the cycle of Western civilizations (VAZ, 2002).

Therefore, the aspect of culture and its connection with religion are extremely important, especially in a historical moment in which a cultural identity is being sought in a reality plunged into an unprecedented crisis. Thus, in order to achieve this objective, it is essential to search for the origins on which the majestic temple of Western culture was built (SALGADO, 2004).

In this sense, it would be impossible to analyze Western culture – and understand it – without the essential element in its formation: Christianity. In the West, the Catholic Church occupied a prominent position in the constitution of sociocultural values and customs, as well as in the search for a universalist and teleological sense of human actions, as an essential cultural foundation of the Western tradition (HUNTINGTON, 1997).

3 RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN POLITICAL POWER AND RELIGIOUS POWER IN BRAZIL

Participating in the construction of Brazilian national identity, since the discovery, the Catholic Church has become almost co-responsible for social cohesion and colonial unity. According to Freyre, Portuguese colonization was characterized by not bringing dissidence or separatism to the colony (FREYRE, 2003). Therefore, Catholicism with a Lusitanian side seems to have, in part, collaborated in this aggregating trait. Thus, since the settlement and occupation of Brazilian territory, the relations between political and religious power are shown to be complementary, even though they present moments of distance and proximity. They are always present in the public space, precisely in the field of power, in their complex interconnection, as Esquivel says, “juxtaposed in the state-Catholic bond” (2003, p. 193).

In Brazil, the participation of religion, specifically the Catholic Church, in the construction of its national identity has proved to be very important since the discovery. The administrative system had a certain dependence on the ecclesiastical apparatus, due to population records, since the clerics were responsible for registering the social life of the communities, from birth, with baptism, until death, since the cemeteries were under the administration of the parishes. Furthermore, numerous members of the clergy took a decisive part in the independence movements, since the time of the Inconfidência Mineira, sharing “a confused amalgam of doctrines and theories that not a few clerics shared” (AZEVEDO, 1978).

The Reformed Christians were present in the colonization period, as well as their missionaries, in the attempts of territorial occupation with the French and Dutch. However, due to the Iberian counter-reformist impetus, it would be from the end of the 19th century that the presence of Protestantism would become remarkable. Since the arrival of German Lutheran immigrants, who came to the South of Brazil and Espírito Santo and, later, the importance played by educational institutions, linked to the Presbyterian Church and the Methodist Church, installed by Confederate refugees from the Civil War in the United States United States of America coming to the interior of São Paulo, in the cities of Americana and Piracicaba, there was an emphasis on the Protestant presence in the country. In turn, the insertion of Evangelical Christians in the country took place in the first decade of the 20th century with American missionaries in Belém, PA, with the foundation of the Assembly of God, in 1910 (FREESTON, 1993).

The 1824 Constitution, from its Preamble, brought a series of devices regulating and legitimizing the Catholic Church, so that the *imperial power* could make use of *religious power*. as a form of legitimation and social cohesion. Through the *Padroado* , the public power interfered in the Catholic Church, a situation identical to that of Colonial Brazil, where all papal bulls and encyclicals depended on the approval of the secular power, that is, of the Emperor ⁹. Ecclesiastical matters were dispatched like any other issue of the imperial administration, with the clergy considered as mere officials of the crown (OLIVEIRA, 1964). Tired of the Empire's meddling in its internal affairs and with disagreements fueled by disputes between the Catholic episcopate and imperial power, culminating in the *Religious Question* , the Roman Church would go through a period of displeasure and even opposition to the monarchy. Therefore,

⁹ It can be observed that articles 103, 106 and 141 of the Constitution of the Empire provided that the Emperor, his Heir, the State Councilors, before assuming power, should swear to maintain the Catholic religion as the official religion. Furthermore, among the Emperor's attributions was to appoint bishops and control ecclesiastical benefits, as determined by article 102, items II and XIV of the Constitution of the Empire. BRAZIL. [Constitution (1824)].

although apparently shy, he offered support to the new republican regime that extinguished the Padroado and that made possible the ecclesiastical reorganization in the country (MALATIAN, 2001).

A of January 7, 1890 separated the State from the Church. The promulgation of the Republican Constitution of 1891 instituted the separation between both institutions according to the legal-constitutional orientation, inspired by American and European liberalism. Apparently, the relations between political and religious power were shaken, officially defining the secularity of the Brazilian State, since it did not allow any religious interference in the public sphere, especially in political power (GOMES, 2008).

The Constitution of the Republic implemented the secular regime, since its Preamble, in which there is no mention of God, unlike the Letter of 1824, which began “In the name of the Holy Trinity”. The Constituent Power did not seek any legitimation, with regard to the legal-constitutional in religious power, as well as rejected an alliance between the State and any religion, according to art. 72, §7, preferring religious neutrality. However, the clergy did not come into conflict with the new rulers, following the guidance given by Pope Leo XIII, who urged agreement and avoidance of friction with the country's new regime (GOMES, 2008) . In this way, the Catholic hierarchy could reorganize itself, subdividing the immense territorial extensions of the dioceses of colonial times and the empire into smaller ecclesiastical circumscriptions. These would have greater ease in episcopal administration and would continue to count on the support of state oligarchies, the economic elite and the benefits of high political spheres, since Church and State had something in common: “the policy of maintaining order” (MANOEL, 1996).

The social transformations that occurred in the legal-constitutional plan of the Old Republic did not have the strength to change the relations with the Catholic Church, constituted since the time of the Colony, passing through the Empire and permeating the period of the implantation of the new republican regime. Thus, considering that the country was still predominantly Catholic and, therefore, although informally, religion exerted great influence over the population, a tacit alliance was established between the temporal and spiritual powers, consummated with the conciliation with the Republic. . (MALATIAN, 2001).

In this perspective, the 1930s were marked by the consolidation of the *reciprocal collaboration* between Church and State, evidenced in the elaboration of the 1934 Constitution. The friendly relations between the dictator Getúlio Vargas and Cardinal Leme, characterized the Estado Novo period, establishing privileged relations of Catholicism with the State, boasting a *status of quasi-official religion* (MARIANO, 2001).

However, in the same period, religions of African origin underwent repression and police persecution, with invasions of terreiros, especially in Salvador (CORREA, 1998). Part of this prejudice came from the modernization discourse, heir to classical evolutionary theories, which associated Afro-Brazilian religions with witchcraft, charlatanism and beliefs. Unfortunately, these prejudices persist and can still be observed in our society.

The proximity between Catholicism and civil power overcame the positivist pretensions of rupture at the beginning of the Republic and continued to exert its influence, greater than any other Christian denominations. The State continued to meet the demands of Catholicism, through tax exemption and, in return, the Church took charge of the formation of the elites, economic and political, in its colleges and universities. Therefore, the true separation between Church and State seems to have occurred with Afro-Brazilian religions, either through discrimination or through harsh persecution (ORO, 2011).

However, it is observed that the force once represented by the Catholic Church in the Latin American continent, has lately been showing itself to be somewhat weakened. Today, the institution faces several challenges, such as the fight against religious indifferentism and secularization, as well as the decrease in the number of believers and the fall in socio-political and economic influence, threatened by the Neo-Pentecostal Evangelical Churches and new religious movements, which have been growing in influence and strength. policy across Latin America (CARTER; GÓMEZ; LUÑON, 2019).

Since the end of World War II, and especially after the 1960s, countless social and political changes have transformed society and cultural and political values. The Second Vatican Council (1962-1965) brought about substantial changes in the systematic form of the *Romanization process*¹⁰ and in the Vatican policy of centralizing ecclesial decisions in the Roman Curia, which began in the 19th century and lasted until the conclusion of the conciliar works, in the mid-1990s. sixty of the last century, as it delegated to the Episcopal Conferences the ecclesial organization in each country (MANOEL, 2004). The Council sought to renew the profile of Catholicism, through *aggiornamento*, that is, an update to the values of modernity. Furthermore, the ecclesiastical administrative structure abandoned the traditional aristocratic perspective and began to identify with the most humble and suffering and, consequently, abandoned the old triumphalism, becoming the *Church of the Poor* (COMBLIN, 2002).

¹⁰Vatican policy of centralization of ecclesiastical decisions in the Roman Curia - started in the 19th century, and which lasted until the conclusion of the conciliar works, in the mid-sixties of the last century (MANOEL, 2004).

In the mid-1970s, the leadership of the National Conference of Bishops of Brazil (CNBB) began to gradually move away from its secular ties with the country's powerful economic and political elites, approaching the popular strata. The old ally of the oligarchies became the *Church of the Poor*, based on the *preferential option for the poor*, origin of the so-called *Catholic progressivism*, represented by *Liberation Theology*, in defense of life, the poor and Human Rights (ORO, 2005). Although not the entirety of the episcopate thought so, the middle class and the elite were moving away and becoming indifferent to the hierarchy and the new precepts of conciliar Catholicism, because they felt abandoned by this *new way of being Church* (CNBB, 1982).

And, in this context of transformations, which began in the late sixties and expanded in the eighties of the twentieth century, added to the expansion of other religious denominations, as well as changes in the economic, social, cultural and intellectual planes, allows us to understand part of the basis of the decline of the political hegemony of Catholicism in the country.

Even if there was no unanimity in the episcopate, the change in positions in Catholicism coincided with the height of *the military dictatorship* (1964-1985) in the so-called *years of lead*, from 1968 onwards. episcopate, led by figures of the moral stature of Dom Frei Paulo Evaristo Arns, OFM, Cardinal Archbishop of São Paulo, SP, and Dom Hélder Câmara, Archbishop of Olinda and Recife, PE, ended up causing a distance between the members of the command of the dictatorial government and the Catholic hierarchy, as well as a greater proximity of the military regime with the evangelical segments (ORO, 2008).

Accelerating and further expanding the entire scenario of transformations that the country was going through, the rural exodus and migration to large centers brought about rapid social changes. The religious traditions of the old rural context were not suited to the new urban realities. In a reality of poverty, underemployment and social exclusion, in the surroundings of large metropolises, evangelical communities have become a place of welcome and a reference for meeting people from different regions of the country. In addition, *conversion* to evangelical groups led to the adoption of new lifestyles, abandoning the *vices of the world*, especially alcohol, cigarettes and drugs, and valuing family life, stimulating a new life for the *believer* (MARIZ, 1994).

Since the end of the seventies, especially expanded in the mid-nineties of the twentieth century, there has been an increase in religious offerings, made available by the media, firstly by radio and, later, by television channels, which encouraged the participation of people in new movements. religious: the Neo-Pentecostal Churches. Most of the time, this displacement was

stimulated by the promise of solving problems, sometimes as a motto *stop suffering*. This whole scenario of religious options fostered the desire of many people to get to know and, later, join these new communities, increasing the number of adherents of the strands of Neo-Pentecostalism.

All this reality would be increased by *the Theology of Prosperity*¹¹ propagated by most of the Neo-Pentecostal denominations. According to this doctrine, the believer *must take possession* of material goods and use them as a sign of God's Blessing, making material wealth a sign of the predilection of the Most High. The material progress of the believer ended up becoming an important decoy for other people to come looking for churches in order to improve their living conditions, a *Brazilian-style religious capitalism*.

With the reestablishment of democracy in the country, the current Federal Constitution of 1988 was drafted, proving to be closer to religions than the first Republican Constitution of 1891. The participation of religion in the public sphere was expanded by evoking in its Preamble the presence of God and providing in its *corpus* on the collaboration between religions and the State in actions of public interest (ESQUIVEL, 2003). In addition, it grants tax immunity to temples of any cult, as well as provides for the possibility of confessional teaching in public schools and, finally, maintains religious marriage with civil effects. As can be seen, the boundary between the political and the religious is historically undefined and tenuous.

And it was in this new democratic scenario that the political presence of evangelicals began to arouse great interest, especially after the organization of the *Evangelical*¹² Banquet, formed by politicians who defend conservative agendas (PIERUCCI, 1996). This Bench does not constitute an ideologically cohesive political group, even though there is a *right-conservative veneer*. There is no unity among the votes of evangelical deputies in economic and administrative areas. Consisting of 115 federal deputies and 13 senators and, as stated in an interview by the leader of this bench to Anna Virgínia Balloussier, from Folha de S. Paulo newspaper, Federal Deputy Sóstenes Cavalcante (DEM – RJ), aims to reach 30% of the seats in Congress in the 2022 election, increasing by 40 deputies and 11 more senators to those already present in Congress (BALLOUSSIER, 2022).

However, this unity is perceptible in the votes in which they seek to impose their values regarding reproduction, sexuality and, above all, abortion (CORTEN, 1996). And this is one

¹¹Religious branch developed in the United States from the sixties of the twentieth century, within the context of televangelism, spreading the belief that the sign of God's Blessing was the financial progress of the believer.

¹²Multi-party bench, composed of members in the Senate and the Chamber of Deputies, most of them linked to neo-Pentecostal evangelical denominations. This bench was regulated in 2003.

of the biggest problems that reveal the need for a better understanding of the relationship between political and religious power, in an attitude of dialogue, however, of respect and tolerance for divergent opinions.

4 RELIGION IS POWER: THE DISPUTES BETWEEN EARTH AND HEAVEN

The links between religion and politics were formed over the centuries, in the development of different civilizations and cultures. The discussion about the relationship between religion and politics exposes how fragile and misleading religious neutrality can be. The abstraction of a secular State is shown to be possible. However, the principle of secularism does not prevent issues related to life or moral values from being discussed based on religious concepts, since the Christian tradition is rooted in Western culture.

However, a *secularist position*, born in an empty humanism, the result of Modernity, positivism and scientism, had relegated religion to the spheres of private life. It was an attempt at *religious neutrality* in matters of political interest and, apparently, this intention did not materialize. They forgot about the importance of Christianity in the formation and transmission of values and, above all, that they are amalgamated in the cultural strata of a large part of society. After all, democracy and diversity are phenomena that express the dynamics of society in constant transformation, with its cultural, social and political expressions.

The coexistence between political and religious powers finds its structural elements in Brazilian culture, in its system of representations, as highlighted by Ari Oro (2005, pp. 221-222) and Gilberto Velho (1991, p. 129). In Brazil, the participation of religion in the construction of its national identity has been of great importance since the colonial period, with Catholicism having influenced this sociocultural formation (ESQUIVEL, 2003). For this reason, it is necessary to understand the social, legal and, especially, political conflicts related to religious issues, which require a more careful analysis (PONZILACQUA, 2016).

The changes within the Church, after the Second Vatican Council (1962-1965) deepened the sociocultural transformations that were underway. Conciliar Catholicism presented its *new way of being Church*: the preferential option for the poor. However, these poor opted for Evangelical Churches (BETTO, 2016) and facilitated this same option to be taken by a large part of the middle class.

The Neo-Pentecostal denominations had a vertiginous growth in the country. Consequently, as there are no vacant spaces in politics, the distancing of Catholicism from the spheres of power opened space for neo-Pentecostal evangelical leaders to seek to occupy that

niche, claiming equality in the treatment of their interests, as was once dispensed to the Roman Church.

The entry of neo-Pentecostal evangelicals into Brazilian politics originated in the awareness of their numerical importance and the strength of their political capital, driven by the defense of agendas linked to the conservation of customs, especially the fight against abortion and *gender ideology*. . With regard to the defense of Christian values, they are close to Catholic parliamentarians, who meet in *the Roman Catholic Apostolic Parliamentary Front* , especially those linked to the Catholic Charismatic Renewal, as well as the *Life Defense Front (Pro-Life)*, who defends the fight against abortion. These groups of parliamentarians bring together about 311 federal deputies. In a 2020 statement, the representative of the Catholic Parliamentary Front, Federal Deputy Francisco Júnior (PSD - GO) stated that he seeks greater proximity to the Evangelical Banquet, since the topics discussed are very close, because "the values we defend are Christians, are not the property of either the Catholic or the Evangelical" (KER, PASARELLI, 2020).

Political-conservative activism is enveloped in the utopia of restoring politics in the name of the Christian faith. The work of the Catholic Front has stood out in defense of life and the traditional family, in line with the guidelines defended by the Evangelical Bank. This reality demonstrates that both groups are moving in the same direction and that they envision joint action in agendas that address common themes, especially the customs agenda (KER, PASSARELLI, 2020).

However, there is a greater mobilization of neo-Pentecostal parliamentarians around the defense of their own ideals (MACHADO, 2015). The themes opposite to those defended by the politicians of the *Bench of the Bible* are most often associated with evil. Such situations create embarrassment for democratic behavior, especially by fostering intolerance and encouraging hate speech, generating persecution of opponents, seen as enemies and not as differing opinions. These political-religious groups show concern not only with social and sexual values, but, above all, with issues related to telecommunications - essential in the conquest and indoctrination of their faithful (CARTER; GÓMEZ; LUÑON, 2019) and, above all, with the preservation of its power, after all, *religion is power*.

The discrediting of traditional political agents has enabled an opening to the entrance of a moralist discourse, with a religious background, which aims to redeem everything that politics has not been able to fulfill. In addition, the multiplicity of religious denominations, which are not bound by doctrinal or ethical limits, raise their members to elective positions. Most of the time, they are appointed by their leaders in the name of the ideal of renewing politics and

defending Christian values. However, religious discourses go beyond the reasonable boundaries between politics and religion. This has alerted to the dangers of intolerance on the part of these political-religious groups.

The approximation between politics and religion should not be seen simply as a dangerous democratic setback, or even as an attempt to impose a religious hegemony. It is necessary to understand it as a demonstration of the strength of religious values present in Brazilian culture, which need to be analyzed and understood. Difficulties must be overcome with political awareness, respect for dignity and diversity. However, this approximation between politics and religion leads us to reflect on the effects and complexity of this involvement in a plural society like ours.

Democracy offers the opportunity for the various social groups to be represented in Parliament and, furthermore, for their values and concerns to be demonstrated to all. However, the discussion of these topics should not be guided by the imposition of concepts and beliefs on the entire population, but, democratically, provide a space for debate, guided by respect for the diversity of opinions. After all, the secular perspective points to the distance between the political and religious spheres, respecting the principle of religious neutrality in which the State maintains an equidistance between belief and disbelief (PONZILACQUA, 2016) .

In this sense, the purpose of this analysis is to expose, in a broad and panoramic way, the need for this reflection on religious influence in the current context of Brazilian politics.

The exercise of democracy, respect, alliances between the various social movements, minorities and the various sectors of society are essential for the establishment of dialogue that will make it possible to understand the relevance and limits of the religious dimension in the public space.

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